

13th EUROPEAN CONFERENCE ON PRECISION AGRICULTURE – HUNGARY

Budapest, 19-22. July 2021

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS OF ALL THE POSTERS

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FOREWORD

Dr. Gabor Milics, PhD, Conference Chair

July 03, 2021, Hungarian Society of Precision Agriculture, Budapest, Hungary

Dear Reader,

In 2017, at the 11th European Conference on Precision Agriculture (Edinburgh), the ECPA conference organizing committee decided that the right of organizing the next conferences will be 2019 SupAgro (Montpellier, France) and 2021 Hungarian Society of Precision Agriculture (Budapest Hungary).

Without being superstitious, the number “13” did not look good! However, at that time, we never thought about what difficulties would face us in the form of a pandemic by 2021. We had to make very difficult decision on risking the organization in the middle of lockdown, postponing the conference or going to on-line. None of the solutions would be acceptable individually, so we decided to have a hybrid event: the first ECPA organized with the possibility to attend in person or join the conference on-line.

The organizers met challenges in every aspect of the preparatory work. However, in spite of all the uncertainties, we sincerely hope that the 13th European Conference on Precision Agriculture will result in a profitable meeting – attending in-person, or on-line – for everyone and will provide new information and solutions for the challenges that agricultural practice is facing.

We are grateful to the International Society of Precision Agriculture (ISPA) for support in communicating the conference news to the members of the Society. The Hungarian Society of Precision Agriculture and the Organizing team would especially like to thank and congratulate Dr. John V. Stafford, the editor of the proceedings, for the enormous work he has done for the conference during the last couple of months sometimes with very tight schedule and very close deadlines. In addition, the organizers would like to thank all members of the conference Scientific Committee: for the International Committee for their invaluable contribution in supporting the editor and assuring the scientific quality of the communications presented at this conference and the Local Scientific Committee for the help in organizing the program.

We appreciate the financial contribution of all the sponsors of the 13th ECPA conference, and would like to highlight the support from the Ministry of Agriculture, Hungary and would like to especially thank Dr. István Nagy, Minister for Agriculture, Hungary for being the patron of the conference. We would like to express our gratitude to all the authors – without whom there would be no conference - and attendees. At the time of writing this foreword (early July 2021), we already know the poster session can only be organized in the on-line space of the 13th ECPA conference. In spite of the fact that poster presenters will be attending on-line, we hope they will follow the conference and prepare their papers for the next conference, when we can all meet in person!

Finally, as Chair I am grateful to all the conference Organizing Committee for their support, and hard work over the past two years – some have been involved in the process for even longer time – in bidding for and delivering this conference. Preparation for the technical tour takes a long time and requires extra effort from the host farm – KEVE Zrt. – and the cooperating partners, making possible to show PA practices in Hungary. Very special thanks go to the technical tour organizing team! Generally, without the great conference and technical tour organizing team - I had the chance to work with - it would be impossible to do this fantastic work!

We – The 13th ECPA Organizing Committee – are both honoured and delighted to have worked for you and to have helped in showing “Adoption of innovative precision agriculture technologies and solutions” series of ECPA conferences.

Have a great Conference!

Sikeres konferenciát!

Gabor

More information: www.ecpa2021.hu

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COMBINED TRAFFIC CONTROL OF IRRIGATION ON HETEROGENEOUS FIELD

A. Nagy¹, A. Szabó¹, Cs. Juhász¹, B. Gálya Farkasné¹, Á. Kövesdi² and J. Tamás¹

¹*University of Debrecen, Faculty of Agricultural and Food Sciences and Environmental Management, Institute of Water and Environmental Management 138. Böszörményi str. Debrecen H-4032, Hungary*

²*Magtár Kft. 2. Kombájn srt. Szolnok H-5000, Hungary*

Water scarcity will become a fundamental problem that will trigger changes in agricultural cultivation and management practices especially in arid and semi-arid conditions (Falkenmark 2013; Nagy et al., 2018). The trend of annual precipitation is still very uncertain in Hungary, the frequency of drought has already increased significantly strongly due to rising temperatures, and decrease in precipitation in the vegetation periods (Tamás et al., 2015; Juhász et al., 2020). Beside water retention measures, the above needs can only be met in a sustainable way with water and energy-saving irrigation, which presupposes different innovative irrigation solutions, especially in the Central European region. Groundwater, which is predominant in arid areas that are low in surface waters, is the source of irrigation water for central pivot equipment (Sui & Yan, 2017), while in this semi-arid/semi-humid region, surface water is protected to supply linear pivots. Several experiments have been made worldwide to evaluate the efficiency of variable rate irrigation (VRI), and investigate its impact on yield and soil. Based on vegetation status, management zones can be created, which can be effective in water control. The aim of the research was to develop a combined traffic control for water-saving precision sprinkler irrigation system on arable land (85 ha), which is located in the reference area of the Tisza Riven Basin. During the research, a real-time eco-potential measurement methodology for water management was developed for water-saving precision sprinkler irrigation system located in South-East Nyírség, Szabolcs-Szatmár-Bereg county in the North-Eastern region of Hungary. A Reinke 2060 PL irrigation machine with a total structural length of 209.09 m was installed in the field. The type of nozzle used is NELSON R3000, which is equipped with 100 kPa pressure regulators and is located at a height of 2.1 m from the ground. Pivoting operation and VRI operation in linear mode can be distinguished.

The precision grid-based soil sampling was carried out on an agricultural field. Different databases and maps were used to elaborate the soil sampling strategy. Core soil samples in two layers (30 cm and 60 cm) were taken. On the arable land analysed, 102 points were modelled, representing more than 1 sample per hectare (1.19 samples/ha), from a total of 510 samples. The texture and soil water retention parameters were measured to determine soil density, total available water content, gravitational water content. Soil chemical properties were also measured and were examined in the Laboratory of Soils of the University of Debrecen, Institute of Water and Environment Management. After laboratory testing, high precision soil maps and a 3-D model of deep root zone were created to support the establishing of a water saving variable rate irrigation system by selecting and identifying sites for different agro-technical implementations and precision management zones.

Irrigation water calculations for traffic control were based on total available water content. In general, it is advisable to start irrigation when the total available water content (TAW) is dropped to 60% (depletion rate 40%), so it was calculated with this value when calculating the actual moisture content. In order to calculate the amount of irrigation water, it is necessary to know the water loss in addition to the thickness of the layer to be irrigated. The water loss can be calculated based on the field capacity, the actual moisture content and the water content at

wilting point. Total available water content of the upper layer has a minimum value of 4.01% and maximum of 25.85% and with mean values of 11.14% with a standard deviation of 4.12% in the deeper layer. Lower values of available water content were also noted, the minimum was 1.95% with a maximum of 15.94% and mean values were 10.78% with a standard deviation of 4.55%. Based on the depletion rate and TAW, the amount of water loss was calculated expressed in a volumetric %, which had to be converted to mm. Since 1 V/V% means 1 mm moisture in a 10 cm thick layer, the numerical value of volumetric water content% also gives the moisture content stored in 10 cm thick layer in mm, i.e.: 1 t^o% = 1mm/10 cm. The same relation can be used if the amount of irrigation water is to be calculated in mm. Based on this, the percentage distribution of water was determined for application in creating VRI zones (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Available water content at 30 cm depth and VRI based traffic control on the basis of TAW (yellow arrows are the directions of the run of irrigation machine)

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address: 1149 Budapest Angol Street 34.
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e-mail: elnok@preciziosklub.hu
web page: www.preciziosklub.hu
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The Hungarian organisers are pleased to welcome the ECPA conference to Budapest, even in this very difficult pandemic situation. The conference is organised in hybrid form, the presenters and participants can join the event online or in person. With this solution we can reach 400 participants.

The aim of the Ministry of Agriculture is to lead the Hungarian farmers into the digitized era of agriculture. A scientific conference is always the best way to promote development. The conference is focusing on the new scientific results and adoption of innovative precision agriculture technologies and solutions.

Hungarian Society of Precision Agriculture
(Magyarországi Precíziós Gazdálkodási Egyesület)
1149 Budapest Angol Street 34.

For more information, please email: ecpa2021@ecpa2021.hu
Website: <https://www.ecpa2021.hu/>